

A Comparative OCTV Study of The Cochlear Apex in Guinea Pig and Gerbil

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Abstract. We recently demonstrated that the guinea pig cochlear apex functions differently from the rest of the cochlea in a way that departs from the principles of universal tonotopy and travelling wave motion (George Burwood et al. Best frequencies and temporal delays are similar across the low-frequency regions of the guinea pig cochlea. *Sci. Adv.* 8, eabq2773 (2022). DOI:10.1126/sciadv.abq2773.) In order to extend these findings and to examine if such features are present in other low frequency hearing rodents, we measured acoustically evoked vibrations in the cochlear apex of the Mongolian gerbil using optical coherence tomography vibrometry (OCTV), using our minimally invasive mirror preparation. We compared the responses of components of the cochlear partition between the two species in terms of tuning, relative phase delay and amplification. We recorded from three locations in each animal, spaced approximately 0.5 turn apart from one another, termed Apical, Middle and Basal. The Basal recording location in gerbil had a characteristic frequency (CF) distinct from the other two locations, and a positive group delay was accumulated between the two basalmost locations. However, the Apical and Middle locations, located 1 and 0.5 turns more apical from the Basal location respectively, shared similar tuning and there was substantial negative group delay between these two locations. All three locations shared the same CF in the guinea pig, and negative group delays were present between all three locations, although the extent and magnitude of these negative delays was smaller between the Apical and Middle location, relative to gerbil. Rather, a constant, small negative delay was measured between the Middle and Basal locations. This delay became positive at higher SPL or after gain was abolished. Two low frequency hearing rodents share similarities in terms of tuning and energy propagation in their cochlear apices. Importantly, the findings in gerbil extend and support the concept that low frequency encoding does not rely on place coding, and that conventional travelling waves may not always be present in the cochlear apex. The results provide comparative insight into the region of the inner ear that is dedicated to frequency bands often used in communication.

INTRODUCTION

The mammalian cochlea is subject to two classical and universal principles regarding its global function. First, each frequency is encoded at a specific organ of Corti (OoC) place – the frequency with the maximal response of that place is termed the characteristic frequency (CF) or best frequency (BF), and the concept is termed tonotopicity [1, 2]. The frequency gradient emerges from the longitudinal variation of stiffness and mass along the basilar membrane (BM). At the basal turn, the BM has less mass and is stiffer, and at the apex of the cochlea it is more massive and compliant. These properties produce a longitudinally varying resonant frequency. With some specific exceptions, such as echolocating bats [3], this tonotopicity is thought to vary systematically from base to apex in all mammals [4].

The second principle is that the sound induced displacement of the BM reaches its resonant place via a slow moving travelling wave – a wave that is driven by propagating pressure changes across the scalae [1]. Such a travelling wave is characterized by a fast and a slow component, where little phase accumulation occurs at frequencies below the CF, while rapid phase accumulation occurs at the CF place (e.g. [5]). Importantly, the travelling wave from incoming sound always travels towards the apex and away from the base – so successively more apical portions of the organ of Corti lag more basal ones [1]. These principles and their underlying mechanisms are fully present in the well-studied basal portion of the mammalian cochlea [6-14]. On the other hand, comparatively little is known about the anatomically remote and bone encased cochlear apex – where low frequency sounds are encoded [15].

The advent of optical coherence tomography has allowed non-invasive imaging through the cochlear bone and thus study of the fully intact apex. Several studies have yielded unexpected findings about the closed apex [16-21]. Our own prior study demonstrated that tonotopicity did not extend to the apical 20% of the guinea pig cochlea, and that group delays between OoC portions in this region shared a surprising amount of physiologically vulnerable temporal coherence – relatively distant OoC longitudinal locations had little difference in group delay at the CF [22].

Our objective was to record data from a different species to confirm our guinea pig findings. The Mongolian Gerbil shares similar low frequency hearing range to the guinea pig. We used our minimally invasive preparation [17] to measure sound evoked OoC vibration in the gerbil and compare the recordings to previously reported guinea pig data.

We found that the gerbil apex does indeed depart from tonotopicity like in guinea pig. We also observed that group delay relationships between successive recording locations do not necessarily support traditional forward travelling wave theory in both species. These observations support our findings that the apex of the mammalian cochlea may transduce sound via mechanisms distinct from the base.

METHODS

All procedures were conducted in accordance with ethical guidelines and with the permission of the local IACUC committee. Animals were anesthetized using ketamine and xylazine with supplemental doses given to maintain areflexia. Briefly, the cochleae of 6 gerbils and 7 guinea pigs were exposed via the ventral approach, as described previously [22]. The surgical approaches were similar between the species.

A gold sputter coated square of cover slip measuring approximately 2 mm² was placed inside the bulla facing the apex of the cochlea. In the case of the gerbil, a 3D printed scaffold was often used to support the mirror in a position that allowed for visualization of the axial plane of the cochlear apex. The scan line from a Thorlabs Telesto III SD-OCT microscope (SLD central wavelength 1300 nm) with a 5 x objective lens was drawn on the mirror and three locations from the cochlear apex were visualized. The locations were spaced approximately 0.5 turns apart, and were described as Apical, Middle and Basal in terms of their relative position (Fig. 1, A: Gerbil, B: Guinea pig). Throughout the paper, red, black and blue data correspond to the Apical, Middle and Basal locations respectively.

Calibrated, logarithmically spaced multitone complexes with random phase were delivered via a closed acoustic system coupled to the ear canal. Displacement and phase were measured from each of the three locations for SPLs ranging from 34 to 74 dB SPL. Measurements were taken in living animals, and following euthanasia via overdose of anesthetic. Reference measurements were also taken from the head of the stapes.

Figure 1: OCT structural scan of the gerbil (a) and guinea pig (b) cochlear apices. Scale bars = 500 μ m.

Displacement and phase were extracted using an algorithm described prior [23]. They are reported as the median of the pixels whose signal to noise ratio exceeded 6 dB, taken from a region of interest encompassing the cellular component of the OoC (excluding the BM). Phase re: middle ear at each frequency was used to calculate group delay

via fitting of a 3rd order polynomial and taking local slopes of the resulting interpolated phase-frequency transfer function. Data from individual animals are displayed for displacement and group delay, and the mean of these data are displayed (thick lines). Cutoffs were defined as -3 dB re: peak displacement on the high side of the tuning curve.

RESULTS

Figure 2 shows the displacement tuning curves for the three locations of each species for gerbil at 34 to 54 dB SPL (A-C) and postmortem at 74 dB SPL (D) and guinea pig at 34 to 54 dB SPL (E-G) and post mortem at 54 dB SPL (H). The Apical location in gerbil appears to have broad low-pass tuning (Red lines, A) that becomes more low-pass at higher SPL (red lines, C). The Middle location, 0.5 turns more basal, shows more band pass tuning (black lines, A) which becomes more pronounced at higher SPL (black lines, C), and is generally of higher displacement than that of the Apical location. The Basal location, a full turn more basal re: the Apical location, displays distinct and relatively sharp band-pass tuning (blue lines, A) possessing a distinct tip and tail region absent from the other two locations. Overall, it appears that the two most apical locations in the guinea pig apex, spaced 0.5 turns apart, show similar tuning if dissimilar displacement, while the most basal location shows different tuning.

Figure 2: Iso-intensity tuning curves from three OoC locations within the apex of the gerbil (N=6, A-D) and guinea pig (N=7, E-H) cochleae. Apical (red), Middle (black) and Basal (blue). Thick lines are the mean response of the individual experiments. SPL and species are indicated in each graph. D and H are taken from the same preparations in A-C and E-G post-mortem, respectively.

In contrast, the tuning curves derived from the guinea pig apex all possess similar tuning, in terms of their high frequency cutoffs. Note also that the frequency range of the responses across the three locations is half that in guinea pig compared to gerbil (Fig. 2 A-C X axes vs. E-G X axes). The most Apical location in guinea pig has distinct band-pass tuning, which changes little with increasing level (Fig. 2 E-G, red lines). The Middle location displays distinct low-pass tuning at 34 dB SPL (Fig. 2. E, black lines), that becomes band-pass as SPL is increased (Fig. 2. G, black lines). This is likely an effect of some mutual suppression in the lower frequencies of the multi-tone complex but indicates non-linearity is present at low frequencies at the Middle location. The Basal location (Fig. 2 E-G, blue lines) is band-pass and has the most displacement at low SPL. Increasing SPL leads to a shift of the peak displacement to higher frequencies (Fig. 2. E vs. G, blue lines). However, all three locations have similar high frequency cut-offs.

Postmortem, the gerbil response at the Basal location (Fig. 2 D, blue) became band-pass, with a CF remaining distinct from the two other locations. However, the peak around the tip region diminishes, partially due to loss of non-

linearity at the low frequencies, and loss of amplification at the higher frequencies. For the postmortem response in guinea pig, (Fig. 2H), the response at all three locations becomes comparable and band-pass in nature – with the bandwidth diminishing as a function of distance from the helicotrema.

These results demonstrate that a departure from tonotopy is present in both species, and that this departure is dependent on the proximity to the helicotrema. The departure from tonotopy also does not depend upon the cochlear amplifier, although amplification enhances tonotopy where it does exist.

Figure 3 shows summary box plots for absolute -3 dB re: peak frequencies for each location and level, for each species in vivo and postmortem. Gerbil in vivo (Fig. 3 A) shows that the Apical (red) and Middle (black) -3dB re: peak frequencies are comparable, while those of the Basal region (blue) are not. There is no consistent effect of SPL on the cutoff value for any location.

Figure 3: -3 dB re: peak cutoff frequencies of OoC responses within the apex of the gerbil (N=6, A, C) and guinea pig (N=7, B, D) cochleae. Apical (red), Middle (black) and Basal (blue). Box and whisker plots represent mean, interquartile range and standard deviation from the mean. Plus signs indicate outlier values. Location is abbreviated on the X axis (A-Apical, M-Middle, B-Basal) and SPL is indicated. B and D are postmortem measurements taken from the same preparations in A and C, respectively.

The cutoff frequencies for the guinea pig are shown in Fig. 3B. Here, all three locations are tuned to comparable frequencies. The Apical cutoff frequencies do not change strongly with SPL (Fig. 3B, Red). A small negative change with decreasing SPL is visible for the Middle location (Fig. 3 B, black), while a stronger level dependent change is evident for the Basal location (Fig. 3B, blue).

Postmortem values for the gerbil were only robust at higher SPLs (Fig 3. C). The Basal location cutoff lowered after death due to the loss of the peak region. The cutoffs for the other two locations did not change postmortem.

Postmortem cutoff frequencies for the guinea pig were similar to in vivo for the Apical location (Fig. 3 D, Red). The Middle location cutoff frequencies increased on average (Fig. 3 D, Black). This occurrence was mirrored in the Basal data (Fig. 3 D, Blue) – and the level dependent changes vanished postmortem. These analyses of absolute cutoff frequencies in gerbil and guinea pig support the finding of a non-tonotopic region of the extreme apex of both species.

Figure 4 shows the summed group delay between the cochlear measurement locations. The group delay at the Apical location re: the Middle location is shown for gerbil (N=6, Fig. 4 A) and guinea pig (N=7, Fig. 4 B). The relative group delay difference between the two locations at 34 dB SPL, where the active component dominates the mechanical response, is negative below the cutoff frequency (vertical dotted line). Above the cutoff, there is a limited bandwidth where the group delay sum is positive. For the guinea pig, a similar pattern is seen, except that the extent of the negative group delay is more limited, and there is no zero crossing associated with the cutoff.

For the group delay measured at the Middle location and referred to the Basal location, in gerbil (N=6, Fig 4C) the delay difference indicates a forward travelling wave which is slow to propagate at low frequencies, becoming faster and more in phase (close to zero delay difference) near the cutoff of the Middle location (Fig. 4C, black vertical dotted line). In contrast, the relative group delay between the Middle and Basal locations in guinea pig (N=7, Fig 3D), show small positive delay, becoming negative delay close to the cutoff of both regions (black and blue vertical dotted lines).

Finally, Fig. 4E-H shows the relative group delays from the post-mortem condition. In the gerbil, responses dropped into the noise floor and so group delay from higher level responses from the linearized cochlea are shown.

Pronounced changes in group delay behavior can be seen in the Apical-Middle 64 dB SPL response from the post-mortem gerbil (Fig. 4 E), and in the Middle-Basal 64 dB SPL response from the post-mortem guinea pig (Fig. 4, H). Figure 5D shows that the frequency range of the negative Middle-Apical group delay difference extends to above the cutoff frequency (Fig. 4E, red vertical dotted line) on average. This, and the in vivo negative delay, implies that this

travelling wave relationship is not necessarily dependent upon amplification. Indeed, the equivalent guinea pig data imply the same (Fig. 4F), and the remaining positive group delay extent for the Middle-Basal group delay in gerbil (Fig. 4G). As previously reported [22], the minimized or negative group delay between the Middle and Basal locations are abolished by higher level and death in the guinea pig model (Fig. 4H).

Figure 4: Relative group delay of OoC responses between measurement locations in the gerbil (N=6, A: Apical-Middle, C: Middle-Basal) and guinea pig (N=7, B: Apical-Middle, D: Middle-Basal) cochleae. SPL is indicated. Vertical dotted lines indicate the mean -3 dB cutoff frequency for each location (Red: Apical, Black: Middle, Blue: Basal). E-H: Relative group delay of organ of post-mortem Corti responses between measurement locations in the gerbil (N=6, E: Apical-Middle, F: Middle-Basal) and guinea pig (N=7, G: Apical-Middle, H: Middle-Basal) cochleae. SPL is indicated. Vertical dotted lines indicate the mean -3 dB cutoff frequency for each location (Red: Apical, Black: Middle, Blue: Basal).

CONCLUSION

Here, we examine the nature of apical cochlear displacement across three sequential half turn separated locations in the gerbil and guinea pig. As in our prior reports on guinea pig, the gerbil apical locations measured from display a lack of tonotopy which is not dependent upon the physiological state of the preparation (Fig. 2). The group delay relationships between these locations are physiologically vulnerable but the basic findings of small or negative group delay relationships between relatively distant locations is comparatively confirmed in a second species (Fig. 5).

The two findings above are not manifested identically between the two species. There is a parsimonious explanation for this: the cochlear length of the gerbil is approximately half that of the guinea pig, and thus the same mid modiolar scanning trajectory bisects twice as much cochlear length – 20% in the guinea pig, and 40% in the gerbil (hence double the frequency range of our measurements in gerbil vs. guinea pig (Fig. 2-5). Thus, it is obvious that the gerbil Basal location is more basal than in guinea pig – and the presence of tonotopy is therefore unsurprising and is expected. That the gerbil dataset shows both regions which are tuned differently (e.g. Fig 2A), and those which are tuned to similar CFs, provides strength to the latter observation. There is clearly need for further study with continuous measurement sites along the cochlear length to improve the longitudinal resolution of these data.

The gerbil Middle and Apical locations are most comparable to the guinea pig data, and their group delay relationships imply that the mechanical behavior of the rodent apex changes with distance from the helicotrema. Such a change from tonotopic to broadly tuned cochlear regions, and from positive delay dominated to negative delay dominated regions, implies a point where neither case dominates. Perhaps this is why we see a frequency invariant, small or zero delay relationship between the Middle and Basal locations in the guinea pig at low SPL (Fig. 4D).

The source of negative group delay relationships can be from the directionality of the travelling wave – but where negative delays dominate, we may be measuring some reflected component of the forward wave from the

boundary represented by the termination of the OoC. In guinea pig, the increase in Apical displacement following death [22] implies expansive non-linearities are present, and these may serve to suppress some of the back reflection.

In summary, both the gerbil and guinea pig apical OoCs can lack tonotopy and show wave propagation characteristics that are distinct from the basal turn, the mechanisms of which, while unclear, merit further study given that they are not unique to the guinea pig.

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DISCUSSION:

[Dennis Freeman]: Thank you for your work in characterizing mechanics of the cochlear apex. Your current comparison of apical mechanics in the guinea pig and gerbil is very interesting.

I have a question about your use of multitone complexes as stimulus. Did you control for possible interactions and/or frequency leakage between components of those complexes? If you were to omit one frequency component from such a stimulus, how close to zero would the cochlear response be at the omitted frequency?

[George Burwood]: Thank you for your query. It's my opinion that the non-linear interaction of components of multitone complexes is clearly not negligible – Erika Fallah and colleagues (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heares.2019.04.001>) demonstrated enhanced compression in the organ of Corti response at the basal turn of the guinea pig cochlea when using multitones versus single tones and thus the responses are producing mutual suppression at higher SPL. Indeed, in our own 2022 paper on guinea pig apical mechanics (DOI: 10.1126/sciadv.abq2773), we discuss the differences in organ of Corti response between single tone and multitone stimuli. I would say that the benefit of the multitone stimulus is one of speed, allowing for optimized OCT experiments (where scanning is slow versus the time axis of the experiment, and hearing sensitivity changes). It gives an interpretation of the tuning that holds the caveat of non-linear interaction, but for experiments such as this, where multiple locations receive the same stimulus and respond differently, one can interpret these differences legitimately. As for the energy at noise bins between tones, or when a tone is absent, I have not made that check myself yet, but I'd be happy to do so and tell you how it turned out.

[Sebastian Meenderink]: I really like how you approach the apical turns using a mirror. Seems that this is the way to look at the organ of Corti&BM from “the right angle”. In this approach, could you give any indication of the angle of the BM in the direction of the longitudinal axis? It seems that there may be a considerable slope here, especially when winding from your basal to middle turn.

[George Burwood]: Thank you for your questions. For multiple locations, changes in angle of incidence between the organ of Corti structures and the OCT beam are likely to influence the overall magnitude of the displacement measurement. Indeed, the longitudinal slope of the BM should introduce relative phase differences between structures that are akin to yours and Wei Dong's experiment (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-022-04234-7>). Interestingly, I have noted that, at least in the guinea pig data, the sign of the phase difference between OoC and BM does not change between the Middle and Basal locations. You could imagine that being on opposite sides of the spiral, the longitudinal distance of the BM from the helicotrema changes – that is that the BM is closer than the RL on one side, and further away on the other. This is a mini version of your great angle change experiment, but it does not introduce a lag-lead relationship flip. My assumption is therefore that the effect of longitudinal slope of the BM is likely small, or that the angle from the beam is small, or that there is less longitudinal entrainment in the guinea pig compared to the gerbil. The slope angle of the BM is definitely something we can look into with this dataset though – we made 3D structural scans of the mirror projected image.

[Sebastian Meenderink]: Also, could you elaborate on the ROI you use to calculate the median response in each animal? If anything, it seems that OCT recordings have shown that the organ of Corti does not respond “as one”, even in the most apical turn (e.g., Cooper et al, 2023; ARO MO131 for apical responses). Taking a grand average across the entire organ seems incorrect, both for amplitude and phase responses. Also, why do you resort to using the median and not the mean? How many pixels remained in each oC/ROI after your 6-dB noise criterium? And what is the variation around the median value?

[George Burwood]: Yes, the ROI is the cellular component of the organ of Corti, excluding the TM (presumably, we cannot see it) and the BM. This includes the supporting and sensory cells and fluid spaces. We have a paper that is close to publication in Hearing Research that addresses the observations of heterogenous phase and displacement behavior in our guinea pig dataset – we have made a row and column wise analysis of phase and displacement values to check whether specific location measurements change our findings re: group delay coherence and tuning. In short, we have not found that they do so in guinea pig. Secondly, the median value reduces the effect of outlier pixels, reducing noise, and improves the precision of fits. This is also checked in the paper, with in vivo data and using a piezo target. We also reduce the influence of a small portion of poorly reflecting pixels that introduce phase flips. This is also discussed in the upcoming paper.

Re: the pixel number, it depends on SPL. At higher SPLs, hundreds of pixels contribute to the median value. At lower SPL, the number can be dozens. The amount also varies with location, as the displacement is smaller for more apical regions. For example, a 34 dB SPL multitone stimulus will produce 181 responding pixels after SNR criterion is applied at the Basal ROI. For the Apical ROI, the number is closer to 50. Our Hearing Research paper is currently in revision and will give much more detail than I can here.

[Sebastian Meenderink]: As for the phase (group delay), I really think that phase data should be shown rather than the difference in slope of two polynomials fitted to these phase data. For one, I can imagine very strong “edge effects” (at low- and high-freq ends) in these fits. If anything, you should subtract the phase responses at two locations, and fit that difference with a polynomial to get at the group delay. But I think it is better to show the actual data.

[George Burwood]: We are comparing local slope versus frequency, not the difference in slope of two polynomials, so the edge effects should be independent and not affect interpretation of mid-frequency group delay differences, which are supportive of our observation of delay coherence (e.g. figure 4 D). I agree edge effects are a problem and limit the interpretability of the extreme frequencies where responses are small, though. Showing the raw phase values corrected for middle ear is useful, and examples of that phase data for the guinea pig dataset are published in our 2022 paper.

[Sebastian Meenderink]: Also, in auditory nerve fiber responses, group delay is (strongly) correlated with CF (e.g. Palmer&Shackleton, 2008 (doi:10.1007/s10162-008-0151-x) or Kim et al, 1980 (doi:10.1121/1.384297)), both for CF and non-CF stimuli. Your gerbil data (Fig. 3a and figs 4/5) seems to indicate that this is not so in the mechanical responses. Maybe am I misinterpreting the y-axis in these latter two figures. But if true, do you have any idea what may cause this difference?

[George Burwood]: Looking at Figure 7 of Palmer & Shackleton, there is an overall correlation but the low frequencies at low SPL (crucial for comparison to our data, where the small group delay differences are only present close to threshold), between 100-300 Hz, show a clustering of fibers with group delays comparable to those lowest. In my figure 4 (note figures 4 and 5 were combined per editorial request), the delay difference between guinea pig Apical and Middle locations at those frequencies is positive, and so the phenomenon of no group delay difference is not present throughout the entire apex, but a portion of it. Gerbil data seem to support that the Middle location has a longer group delay than the Apical location below CF. I think this could be related to the reversal of the OoC width gradient closer to the helicotrema which has been shown to be the case in guinea pig (Yarin et al. 2014 DOI: 10.1007/s10162-013-0420-1). Using Tsuji and Liberman’s map, the dimensions of the guinea pig organ of Corti are constant from the 750 Hz location to the 100 Hz location, and it becomes smaller again closer to the helicotrema. If the width is predictive of the CF, locations between 750 Hz and 100 Hz should have the same CF, and CF would increase after that. So mechanically, we lose this correlation in this region, and that might affect the group delay of a small number of fibers. Whether this also influences the direction of wave propagation I do not know, but it should be noted that negative group delay relationships do not necessarily mean this – such delay relationships can happen in anomalous dispersive systems, for example.

I think we might be looking at a form of acoustic fovea. My speculation is that if CF is not a component of frequency encoding in the apex, then auditory nerve position relative to group delay may not always be correlated. So, then a 200 Hz fiber putatively responding from the region identified in our mechanics measurement might be closer to the Middle, or Basal location and yet does not have a group delay that would reflect its position like for higher CF fibers. Also, if you look at Recio Spinoso and Oghalai’s 2017 paper (DOI: 10.1113/JP273881) and observe the low frequency fibers from Nigel Cooper’s work superimposed upon their threshold tuning curves, 3/6 of the curves with a cutoff frequency of around 500 Hz have minimal or no low frequency shoulder, and have low threshold across a wide frequency range. Other fibers are present, tuned slightly higher, which have broad, V shaped threshold tuning curves. The authors of that paper concluded that vibratory thresholds do not match neural thresholds below CF in their data, while I think some of them match excellently and might be distinct in their behavior. As our coherent behavior vanishes at higher SPL, perhaps there are untuned fibers and tuned fibers present in this region of the cochlea, that respond optimally to different regimes (active dominated vs. passive dominated).

I would not comment on Kim’s paper as cat and chinchilla data are harder to directly compare to guinea pig or gerbil given that the comparative differences in group delay behavior highlighted in this paper are quite evident.